

Dynamics Of Infographic Variables In Education: A Modelling And Simulation Approach

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 21,2023</p> <p>Accepted: February 22,2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Infographics In Education, Infographic Creation, Compare And Contrast Information, Digital Literacy Enhancement, Summarizing In Infographics, System Dynamics Simulation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10689713</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this research is to study the influence of calculation efficiency on the five dimensions that define infographic, namely –creating, enhancing digital literacy, and summarizing in the context of education. A positivist paradigm of research has been chosen and modelling and simulation technique using System Dynamics has been adopted. Results indicated that in terms of creating the infographic, the calculation efficiency had a positive influence, and after the very slow rate of increase in first 10 months of introducing infographics in education, there can be an exponential rise on the number of units of infographics creation. In terms of comparing and contrasting dimension of infographic, when the number of units of creation at the 20th month is about 12 with 80% calculation efficiency, it was about 44 units in case of comparing and contrasting, about 14 units in the case of digital literacy enhancement, and it is about 35 units in the case of summarizing. The implications to the infographic designers is that if short-term gain is the focus, it is advisable to increase the ability to compare and contrast the information provided in the infographic and if the target is long-term gain, it is advisable to increase the ability to summarize the information in infographic both through the increase in the calculation efficiency during the creation of the infographics. Accordingly, suggestions have been made to the infographic designers who could either be the teachers or students who make use of infographics to disseminate knowledge. The outcome of the research could be useful to both the academics as well as practitioners.</i></p>

Introduction

Infographic is now becoming popular in education at all levels as it is found to develop a number of professional skills and capabilities simultaneously, such as digital literacy, visualization capability, information literacy, critical thinking ability, creativity and innovative skills, communication skills, and collaboration skills (Jaleniauskiene&Kasperiuene, 2023). Infographics have become increasingly popular in recent years as a way to visually represent complex data and information in a simple and engaging manner. In the field of education, infographics have the potential to enhance learning by making complex concepts and information easier to understand and remember (Wang et al., 2023). As a result, there has been a growing interest in the use of infographics as a tool for teaching and learning, and a corresponding increase in research on the effectiveness of infographics in educational contexts. It now become a common tool to assimilate as well disseminate knowledge between students and teachers alike owing to its immense capabilities coupled with the ability to make learning or teaching enjoyable.

In the context of education, infographics befits very well into instructional purposes as students are given all necessary information at a glance, which facilitates understanding and memorization. Mocek (2017) suggested using infographic syllabus design to provide essential information, which has been proved beneficial for syllabus information retention and student engagement. Research on infographics in education has focused on a range of topics, including the impact of infographics on student learning and retention, the effectiveness of different design elements in infographics, and the best practices for creating and incorporating infographics into instructional materials (Taye et al., 2023). Studies have also examined the use of infographics in different educational settings, such as K-12 classrooms, higher education, and online learning environments (Lee & Kwon, 2023).

Infographics and simulation models are two powerful tools that can be used together to enhance understanding of complex information and systems (Atwood et al., 2023). Infographics are visual representations of data and information, while simulation models are computer programs that simulate real-world systems or processes (Hai-Jew, 2023; Krestyanpol, 2023). When used in conjunction, infographics and simulation models can help to create a more complete understanding of complex systems by providing both visual and interactive representations. For example, an infographic could provide a high-level overview of a system, while a

simulation model could allow users to interact with the system and see how it responds to different inputs and scenarios. Using infographics and simulation models together can be particularly effective in educational settings, where students may struggle to grasp complex concepts and systems without visual aids or hands-on experiences (Teslyuk et al., 2023). By presenting information in a visual and interactive format, students can better understand complex systems and develop a deeper appreciation for the underlying principles.

While the above are some advantages in using infographics and simulation modes in conjunction, there can also be an approach to simulate the capability of infographics in disseminating knowledge so as to study the multiple scenarios (Kleinbub et al., 2021). There are not many research studies which have taken this approach and to fill this gap the research focus of this paper is on the use of System Dynamics (SD) based modelling and simulation to study the efficacy of the antecedents of design information conversion rate in the creation of infographics.

Theoretical Background

The theoretical background of infographics draws from several fields, including visual communication, cognitive psychology, and data visualization. At its core, infographics are designed to convey complex information in a visually appealing and easily understandable format as mentioned before. In visual communication, the principle of visual hierarchy is an important consideration when creating infographics (Po-An Hsieh, & Wang et al., 2007). This principle emphasizes the importance of arranging visual elements in a way that guides the viewer's attention and creates a clear flow of information. This can be achieved through the use of contrasting colors, different font sizes and styles, and the placement of visual elements on the page.

Cognitive psychology also plays a role in the theoretical background of infographics (Gay et al., 2019). The dual-coding theory suggests that people process information more effectively when it is presented both visually and verbally (Almunive & Alshammari, 2018). This means that infographics can be a particularly effective way of conveying complex information, as they combine visual and textual information in a way that maximizes comprehension.

Data visualization is another important aspect of the theoretical background of infographics (Dur, 2014). Data visualization involves the use of visual elements to represent and communicate data. Infographics often incorporate data visualization techniques, such as charts, graphs, and diagrams, to help viewers understand complex data sets and patterns.

Thus, the theoretical background of infographics draws from multiple fields to create a powerful tool for communicating complex information in a visually appealing and easily understandable format. By considering principles of visual communication, cognitive psychology, and data visualization, infographics can be designed to effectively convey information and enhance understanding.

Visualizing concepts and processes is the start point of the creation of infographics (Shcherbakova, 2023). Infographics can be used to visualize abstract concepts or complex processes, making them easier to understand and remember. For example, an infographic can be used to visualize the steps in a scientific experiment. During the process of visualizing the concepts it is essential that the entire content to be presented has to be broken down into meaningful steps which are sequentially connected to each other (Chun, 2023). Second, the right kind of flow chart and diagrams have to be used to present the content in an appealing manner. Use arrows, symbols, and other graphic elements to show the flow of information or materials through the process will be handy. To help viewers understand the different components of the concept or process, labels and annotations have to be included that provide additional information or context. This can help ensure that viewers understand what they are looking at and how it relates to the overall concept or process (Kneer et al., 2023). Visual metaphors can be a powerful way to convey complex concepts in a way that is easy to understand e.g., using a lightbulb to represent an idea or a road map to represent a plan (Kay, 2023). Finally, colors and fonts can play a big role in how your infographic is perceived. It is important to choose colors that are easy on the eyes and help differentiate different components of the infographic, and fonts that are easy to read and match the tone of the message have to be used (Giorgino et al., 2023).

There are several dimensions that characterize the self-efficacy of infographics as a tool in education among which the four most commonly highlighted dimensions are: *creating, comparing and contrasting, enhancing digital literacy, and summarizing*. While there are other dimensions these are the four basic dimensions of infographics which define the basic structure of infographics (Hernandez-Sanchez et al., 2021; Kapel & Schmidt, 2021; Lu et al., 2020).

Creating visual aids - Infographics can be used as visual aids during classroom lectures or presentations, helping to reinforce important points and engage students. Creating starts with a plan and identification of the purpose (Krauss, 2012). Determination of the purpose of infographic, who the audience is, and what message has to be conveyed form the basic elements (Siricharoen, 2013). This will guide the design decisions and help ensure that the infographic effectively communicates the intended message. Research on topic and gathering of relevant data and information required may include statistics, facts, quotes, or images. Following this, organizing of the content into a clear and logical structure, such as an outline or flowchart is required that will help in determining which elements should be highlighted and how they should be presented (Davidson, 2014). Then comes the selection of a design style that matches the purpose and audience. This could include a minimalist or

colorful design, a data-driven or storytelling approach, or a specific theme or aesthetic. Refining and editing of the design will also be necessary. This could involve tweaking the layout, adjusting colors or fonts, or adding or removing content.

The process of creating infographics is also related to the use of digital tools in higher education as it increase of learners' productivity (Warren and Wakefield, 2013). For instance, the use of a spreadsheet to save quantitative data can illustrate this kind of practice. Instead, educational researchers and practitioners advocate for a more advanced use of technology or its use as mindtools that help to extend cognitive abilities of learners (Shcherbakova, 2023). Jonassen & Land (2000) defined mindtools as computer-based tools and learning environments that have been adapted or developed to function as intellectual partners with the learner to engage and facilitate critical thinking and higher-order learning. Such tools might help to perform tasks in quicker and more professional ways in comparison to students working alone. Accordingly, infographic tools display the characteristics of mindtools or use of technology for a purpose that goes beyond productivity increase.

Comparing and contrasting in Infographics can be used on different topics or ideas, making it easier for students to see the similarities and differences between them. Some of the common methods used include *side-by-side comparison* in which two-column is used to format to display data or information for two or more items (Cui et al., 2019). This allows viewers to quickly see similarities and differences between the items being compared. For example, an infographic comparing the features and prices of different smartphones could use a side-by-side comparison format. *Venn diagram* may be used to show how two or more sets of data or information overlap (Kelly et al., 2019). This can be an effective way to highlight similarities and differences between different groups or categories. For example, an infographic comparing the interests and hobbies of two different age groups could use a Venn diagram to show which activities are common to both groups. *Bar chart* may also be used to visually compare and contrast data sets in infographics (McCrorie et al., 2016). This can be particularly effective for displaying numerical data, such as sales figures or survey results. By using different colors or shading for each data set, viewers can easily see how the data sets compare to each other. *Infographic timeline* may be used to compare and contrast different events or periods of time (Chen et al., 2019). This can be an effective way to highlight changes or trends over time. For example, an infographic comparing the history of two different companies could use a timeline format to show how each company evolved over time. Thus, comparing and contrasting in infographics can help to highlight similarities and differences between different sets of data or information in a clear and easily understandable format.

Enhancing digital literacy is another capability of Infographics as it can be used as a tool to teach digital literacy skills, and students can learn how to create and analyze visual representations of data and information. Infographics can be a powerful tool for promoting digital literacy because they offer an engaging and visually appealing way to present complex information in a concise and accessible format. Infographics can help break down complex information into easy-to-understand digital images, making it easier for students to absorb and retain information (Jaleniauskiene & Kasperuniene, 2023). This can be particularly useful in promoting digital literacy, where technical concepts and jargon can often be intimidating for beginners. Infographics are highly shareable on social media and other online platforms, which can help reach a wider audience and engage people who may not otherwise be interested in digital literacy (Shcherbakova, 2023). By presenting information in a visually compelling way, infographics can capture people's attention and encourage them to learn more. Infographics can help contextualize information by presenting it in a broader context. This can be particularly useful in promoting digital literacy, where it's important to understand how different concepts and technologies fit together and interact with one another (Bećirović, 2023). Infographics can be designed to encourage exploration and discovery, with clickable links and interactive elements that allow people to dive deeper into specific topics or concepts. This can help promote digital literacy by encouraging people to explore new technologies and learn more about how they work.

Summarizing and presenting data is another dimension of Infographics can be used to present data in a concise and easy-to-understand manner, making it easier for students to digest and remember important information. During summarizing and presenting the data and information in infographics it is important to establishing visual hierarchy among elements, clarifying relationships among elements, and draw attention to a significant fact or detail (Shcherbakova, 2023). Summarizing demands deeper processing of knowledge, which promotes meaningful learning and it is essential that the presenter will have to be thorough with the entire content under investigation and find a means to present it in a brief, concise, and succinct manner through the graphics, charts, videos etc., to make it easily understandable as well as remain imprinted in the minds of the students if used in the educational settings (Bećirović, 2023).

The Model Development

Figure 1: Infographic of used in natural sciences

The model (Figure 1) is a widely used infographic in natural sciences. This has been used as the basis for the construction of a simulation model in order to study the influence of the five factors that play a dominant role in promoting the innovation brought about in through infographic-based teaching, namely – calculation, conceptualization, categorization, contextualization, and correction.

Calculation involves the conversion of all the available data into useful information. For instance, the case considered in this research is the infographics on the ecosystem taught in natural sciences. The data has to be obtained on how much one hectare of Pine forest is capable of absorbing every year. The available resources indicate that approximately 20 to 30 tons of Carbon Dioxide is absorbed by this. The infographics involves narration of physical data which includes: 200 to 400 Liters of water that can be released by a tree through evaporation process every day, five air conditioners working 24 hours per day are needed to cool air like a tree does, trees can reduce the air temperature in the neighborhood by 11⁰Centigrate, 118 Kilograms of oxygen that a small tree produces annually, while 176 Kilograms of oxygen is required by a man annually etc. (Bounaceur et al., 2023; Fattah et al., 2023; Sanjuán et al., 2020). So, there are several such calculations which need to be undertaken during the creation of an infographic and the efficiency of calculation in terms of accuracy, speed, representing ability, etc., play a vital role that may affect the design information conversion rate. For the sake of simulation, the efficiency of calculation is taken converted to be a factor and varied from 0.2to 0.8 in steps of 0.2.Causation loop of calculation extends to design *information conversion rate* and *comparing and contrasting*(figure 2)

Conceptualization is another aspect that has a bearing on the infographic design information conversion rate. During the conceptualization, the images are converted into some abstract form that is representative of the theme and it is important that there is no distortion of the central idea when it is recalled (Fowler et al., 2001). It is a well-established fact that human mind can recall images much faster and can remember for a longer duration than words or numbers (Campos et al., 2021). So, the designer of infographics will have to first collect all the images that best represent the concept or idea that has to be presented and then pick the one that is most appealing for a large number of students. It is an iterative and time-consuming process but the success of the project in developing infographics depends on this to a considerable extent. For modelling purpose, the conceptualization ability is also considered as a factor. The causation loop of condensation extends to design *information conversion rate* and *comparing and contrasting* (figure 2)

Categorization, during the design information categorization, retrieval, association, and transformation has to take place (Finke et al., 1992). Retrieval involves the capturing of the images from various sources, mainly the

database where the information is stored. The retrieval time has to be minimum and at the same time the most appropriate diagram or picture must be extracted from the myriad or stored data. The next step would be association during which the picture is associated with the caption and brief explanation that has to be displayed with it. The final step in categorization is transformation where the synergistic effect of the picture and the information is created to produce the desired impact. For modelling purpose, the categorization ability is also considered as a factor. The causation loop of categorization extends to design *information conversion rate* and *comparing and contrasting* (figure 2)

Contextualization, is mainly in terms of ‘sustainability’ and all of its dimensions have to be considered for its effectiveness (Celadyn et al., 2019). Dimensions refer to the factors that define the completeness of the infographic artefact. It can include clarity, color, size, font, spacing, etc. Contextualization in infographics refers to the process of providing relevant background information or context that helps the viewer understand the data being presented (Zia, 2023). The relevant background information should be present in the beginning itself. Depending on the topic, providing historical or cultural context can help the viewer better understand the data being presented. To properly contextualize data in an infographic, the purpose and target audience is to be understood fully. Understanding why the infographic was created and who it is intended for will help determine the appropriate level of detail and type of context needed. Use clear and concise language is another feature. Infographic should be easily digestible and not overwhelm the viewer with unnecessary jargon or technical terms. Simple language should be used to explain any complex concepts or data. Comparing data to relevant benchmarks or past performance can help put the data into perspective and give viewers a better understanding of its significance. Finally, it includes the incorporation of visual aids. Incorporating visual aids such as maps, charts, and graphs can help convey information in a clear and concise manner. On the overall basis, the entire infographic should fit to the context of the presentation and represent the themes involved to the best of its abilities. For modelling purpose, the contextualization ability is also considered as a factor. The causation loop of contextualization extends to design *information conversion rate* and *comparing and contrasting* (figure 2).

Correction refers to the rearrangement of the existing elements in the infographic without breaking the structure (Zhang & Xing, 2021). The information that can facilitate correction has to be processed very efficiently and the most relevant data/information may have to be applied during the process of correction during the creation of the infographic. Many a times the data will be outdated and needs to be updated and the accuracy of correction plays an important role. It is important because a group of students will record the information dissipated through the infographic and use it in their assignments and career building. There must be a mechanism to validate the data and authenticate it before it is brought to the public display. For modelling purpose, the correction ability is also considered as a factor. The causation loop of correction extends to design *information conversion rate* and *comparing and contrasting* (figure 2).

Figure 2: The Stock and Flow Diagram

For all the stock variables used in this research the simulation is undertaken for the number of units of the respective stock for the given amount of variation in the multiple scenarios considered for the calculation efficiency. The detailed equations used in the construction of the model are provided in Appendix-1. The causal loops of the stocks are as follows.

Comparing and contrasting is a stock variable that varies in time and the value in terms of units are based on the *design information archiving rate* and *design information conversion rate*. While the former is influenced by the

stock in *comparing and contrasting*, the latter is influenced by the stock in visualizing and the five factors that affect the design information conversion rate (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Determinants of Comparing and contrasting

The *Creating of infographic* is a stock variable and its value in terms of units are based is dependent on the *information decline rate* and the *information growth rate*. The former is influenced by the stock of creations of the infographic and the latter is influenced by the *creations available*, *enhancement of digital literacy*, and *socialization* between the teachers and the students (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Determinants of Creating infographic

The *Enhancing digital literacy* is a stock variable and its value in terms of units are based is dependent on the *design knowledge obsolescence rate* and the *information advancement rate*. The former is influenced by the stock in *enhancing digital literacy* and the latter is influenced by the stock in *comparing and contrasting*, *stock increasing infographic*, *combination and externalization of knowledge* between the teachers and the students (Figure 5).

Figure 5: determinants of Enhancing digital literacy

The *summarizing in infographic* is a stock variable and its value in terms of units are based is dependent on the stocks *increating infographics* and *enhancing digital literacy*. The former is influenced by the stock in *information decline rate* and *information growth rate* the latter is influenced by the *design knowledge obsolescence rate*, and *Information advancement rate*(Figure 6).

Figure 6: Summarizing in infographic

Results and analysis

The objective of research was to study the influence of the change in *calculation efficiency* involved in infographic creation on the four dimensions infographic in education. Following sections discuss the influence based on the simulation results. The calculation efficiency expressed as a factor was varied from 20% to 80% in steps of 20% and the corresponding change in the four dimensions of infographic. The number in the four stocks under investigation is in the number of units of infographic. The simulation was run for a period of 3 years.

Influence on Creating Infographic

It can be observed that increase in *calculation efficiency* will have no significant influence on the efficiency of creating infographic for the first 10 months of its inception. After this period, the number of units of creation of information through infographic increases with the increase in the calculation efficiency exponentially. Also, the higher the calculation efficiency the higher will be the creations (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Influence on creating infographic

Influence on Comparing and Contrasting

The trend in the increase of *comparing and contrasting* efficiency is same as that observed in creation efficiency; however, the number of units of comparing and contrasting will be almost double. For instance, when the number of units of creation at the 20th month is about 12 with 80% calculation efficiency, it will be about 44 in case of comparing and contrasting (Figure 8). The obvious reason for this increase is that when more and more data is available through creation of infographic it will facilitate the comparison and contrast to a greater extent. This has also been observed by earlier researchers (e.g., López-Pintor et al., 2023).

Figure 8: Influence on comparing and constrasting

Influence on Enhancing digital literacy

The effect of increase in calculation efficiency on *digital literacy enhancement* has been shown in figure .It can be observed that the trend is similar to the previous cases; however, the influence is slightly less than that observed in creating of the infographic. While number of units of creation at the 20th month is about 12 with 80% calculation efficiency it is about 12, it is about 14 units in the case of digital literacy enhancement(Figure 9). While the calculation efficiency is improved the infographics will be more accurate and reliable and hence it has a better impact on the enhancement of digital literacy as in the case of creation of infographic.

Figure 9: Influence on enhancing digital literacy

Influence on Summarizing

It can be observed that the trend is similar to the previous cases; however, the influence is similar to that of comparing and contrasting the information depicted in the infographic. While number of units of creation at the 20th month is about 12 with 80% calculation efficiency it is about 12, it is about 35 units in the case of summarizing ((Figure 10). While the calculation efficiency is improved the infographics will be more accurate and reliable, and hence it has a better impact on the ability to summarize the information on the infographic. Similar observation was made by other researchers in the case of Infographics in higher education (Jaleniauskiene&Kasperuniene, 2023).

Figure 10: Influence on summarizing

Discussions and Implications

The simulation results have shown the trend of variation in the dimensions of research interest in infographics in education. The key observation is that when the calculation efficiency is increased the highest impact in about 2 years of its inception will be on the dimension *comparing and contrasting* (44 units) followed by *summarizing* (35 units) when short term gain (say about 2 years) is the target. On the long run, say in 3 years the highest impact of increasing calculation efficiency is on summarizing (213 units) followed by comparing and contrasting (206 units). The implications to the infographic designers is that if short-term gain is the focus it is advisable to increase the ability to *compare and contrast* the information provided in the infographic and/or if the target is on long-term gain, it is advisable to increase the ability to summarize the information in infographic both through the increase in the *calculation efficiency* during the creation of the infographics. Following are some of the suggestions to the designers of infographic to increase the calculation efficiency while creating the infographic.

First of all, the designer should understand that distilling academic research into an infographic requires a thorough understand of the process of information creation from the available data. Next, it is important to realize the value of the information and how visuals can communicate this information so that the students can comprehend it and apply it in a given situation. Thirdly, it is important to know how infographic acts as a conversation using the Information Literacy and Visual Literacy frameworks (Kalaf-Hughes, 2023).

The calculation of the gap between the desired and current state becomes easy when there is a systematic approach in the creation of the infographic. Following steps may be adopted during the design of the infographic.

1. Determine who your audience is and what information they are interested in. This will help you decide what data to include in your infographic. For instance, it is important to know what is the available knowledge with the students when an infographic is created so that they can relate the knowledge they have to the information provided in the infographic. The best way is to have a list of prerequisite courses and the syllabi of those courses during the preparation of the infographic. This information will provide the base to enhance the calculation efficiency.

2. The next step would be to collect the data required to present in the infographic. The accuracy and reliability of the data play a vital role in enhancing the calculation efficiency.
3. The data thus obtained has to be grouped into categories or themes. This will help in the creation of clear and coherent message. While clarity ensures intelligibility, coherence will provide consistency and orientation to a point.
4. This step should provide the base for choosing the visual elements. It may include charts, pictures, graphs, diagrams, icons, or images.
5. In this step the actual design of the infographic takes place. The design should be visually appealing and easy to read. The choice of colors, fonts, and other design elements to make the infographic engaging and visually interesting becomes important.
6. In this step the context and narrative have to be added. The context and narrative of the infographic helps the audience to understand the data and its significance. This may include captions, labels, or annotations.
7. The final step is to test and refine the infographic. It is worthwhile to test the infographic with a small group of friends and peer-group and make adjustments based on their feedback.

In this research, the dimensions that define the features of infographic i.e., *comparing and contrasting*, and *summarizing* have emerged as the two important factors. The infographic designer has to consider these two factors as most important. The reason is that by comparing and contrasting data in an infographic the differences between two or more data sets can be highlighted easily. This can make it easier for the audience to understand and analyze the data. It also provides a visual impact through graphic representation to compare and contrast data in an infographic that can make a stronger impact on the audience than simply presenting the data in text form. It can also communicate a message or story to the audience. By presenting data in a meaningful way, the infographic can help the audience to better understand the information and its significance. Finally, it can simplify complex information. When dealing with complex data sets, comparing and contrasting information can help to simplify the information and make it more accessible to the audience.

Summarizing also has an equal role in infographic. First of all, it captures the essence. Fundamentally, an infographic is a visual representation of information that is designed to quickly communicate the essence of the data. Summarizing the data is a crucial step in capturing the key points and presenting them in a way that is easy for the audience to understand. Secondly, it simplifies complex information. Infographics often deal with complex information that can be overwhelming for the audience. Summarizing the data helps to simplify the information and make it more accessible to the audience. Summarizing saves time as infographics are designed to communicate information quickly and efficiently. Summarizing the data can save time for both the creator and the audience, as it presents the information in a concise and easy-to-digest format. Finally, it communicates a message. Infographics are often used to communicate a specific message or story. Summarizing the data is an essential part of communicating this message effectively, as it helps to ensure that the audience understands the main point being made.

Conclusion

The education has now entered into the infographic era. There are several research studies which are taking place concurrently across the globe on its relevance, design, applicability, and success. This research has focused on the design aspect of infographic and made an attempt to study the influence of one of the five factors which impact the design information conversion rate in the creation of the infographic.

Modelling and simulation approach has been used to study the impact of five factors on the four dimensions of infographic. Among the five factors that influence the design information conversion rate, the impact of calculation efficiency was of specific interest in this research. The results of simulation identified that for the short term benefit of infographic in dissemination of the knowledge comparing and contrasting would be impacted through the enhancement of calculation efficiency and on the long term basis summarizing would be impacted. Accordingly, suggestions have been made for better design of infographic which may be used by the infographic designers who can be either Teachers/Professors/Professional designers.

The main limitation of this research is that the simulation is based on the data used for the creation of single infographic in the context of basic sciences. So, generalization of the results may not be universal. However, the model may be easily modified to suit to the requirements of other disciplines. Also, a qualitative research follow-up may make the study more authentic. So, these limitations open up further scope carrying out this research.

As the infographic-based teaching is now a global trend and there are studies which have proved that it is going to stay for some time, this research is timely as it is focusing on the enhancement of the efficiency of infographic. The implications drawn may be worth a consideration to the designers of infographic.

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